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IMPACT OF MARKETING RESEARCH ON THE DECISION MAKING

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IMPACT OF MARKETING RESEARCH ON THE DECISION MAKING

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Abstract:

Marketing research is an important factor which plays a vital role in determining and taking decisions about marketing activities. Marketing is the term which starts from customers and ends with customers. This activity starts before production and ends with the satisfaction of the customers. The term customer satisfaction is also one of the major parts of the business. Marketing research intends to gather and gain more detailed information and understanding of customers. Through this one can able to understand the customer and their tastes, preferences, forecast the future and also this helps to reduce the risk of product and business failures. In this paper an attempt has been made to understand the concept of marketing research, its impact on the decision making of a business, effect on consumers buying behaviour etc. through thorough review of literature. Thus critical analysis has been made on the marketing research and its implications on the decision patterns of the company.

Keywords: Marketing Research, Impact on Decision Making, and Prospects of MR.

Introduction

Market research is the unique process of determining the availability and viability of new services and products through research conducted directly with potential customers. The market research may be conducted from home, mobile, internet, or physical observation and collection of data from the end users. This may be carried out by the company itself or by the third party for a return. This is the critical and crucial component of research and development department of a company. Decision making is an important aspect in every business organisation, the good decision making influences on the best performance of the company. Marketing concept can be impacted by many factors such as taste preference of the consumers, demand and supply of products, inflation, economic recession, unemployment, war, terrorism, rapid technological changes etc. in the mid of these all factors if a company wanted to run its business they must adapt and practice market research.

Review of Literature

The study explained the role of marketing research, its importance in decision making and application of marketing research result in daily business activities. It will helpful in identifying the potential customers, understanding the behaviour of existing customers, helps to develop realistic and effective strategies to build brand in the market place, and to identify the new opportunities in the market (**Hamza Ali-Al Shatanawi**). The study focussed on the role of marketing research on the performance of business organisation. The marketing research provides both primary and secondary data for decision making, it analyses both micro and macro environmental factors and their effect, it determines the market segments, target market, market competition, marketing position and tries to forecast the future market for a company (**Bello Ayuba & Aina Olalekan Kazeem**).

Four marketing research performance tools have been identified such as market research as a knowledge enhancing program, internal political use of marketing research, misuse of market research and the generation of market understanding. How strategic orientation relates to the ways market research information used to decision making in the firm (**Bednall David & Valos, Michael**). Marketing strategy is a construct that may lie at the theoretical heart of the strategic marketing and it is the central to the practice of marketing activities. Marketing strategy is an integrated part of decision making that specifies its crucial selection of concerning products, services, markets, marketing activities, resources etc. (**Neil A Morgan et al.**). (**Chaman Sab, Dharani K P & Balabhim S Biradar**). The paper summarises the state of art of industrial market research in India. Also, stressed on orientations of business towards marketing research, the

dominant profile of contemporary marketing research activities and efforts in information collection. Further they highlighted the emerging trends of marketing research those will accelerate the progress of Indian industries (**Sharad Sarin**).

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the factors influencing and the process of market research.
2. To analyses the impact of marketing research on decision making of organisations.

Research Methodology

The present study is explorative and descriptive in nature. Study concentrates on factors contributing to the implementation of marketing research in an organisation and their influence on the performance and decision making. Secondary data have been used to determine the impact of marketing research on the performance and decision making ability of an organisation in the modern era. Those secondary data have been collected from various papers, articles, journals, marketing websites, e-books etc.

Effect of Marketing Research on Decision making in regards with 4 P's.

- ❖ MR helps not only to learn what your customers want but also to know how successful your business is at reaching and connecting with customers.
- ❖ MR helps in identifying new markets and market opportunities for existing as well as new products.
- ❖ MR helps to formulate the best strategies for better future of organisation.
- ❖ MR facilitates the global market to existing and new products and services.
- ❖ Marketing is an activity which starts from customers and ends with customers, thus, it is customer centric. Large production needs mass distribution channels. MR helps in collecting information on customers from well structured distribution channels.
- ❖ Communication plays a vital role in enhancing the business cycle. Hence, MR identifies and facilitates a good and adequate communication tool to share information and all about products. This will be helping in promoting a business in an effective manner.
- ❖ MR helps to identify the sales territories, target market, and target customers. The results of MR may contribute in enhancing the sales force of the organisation.
- ❖ MR collects all round information about demand for the products and customers preferences. Hence, it is possible to forecast future sales and profitability.
- ❖ MR is used to study and find out the existing brand position in the market. It explores the possibilities of prospects of changing existing brand names and extension. MR will be helping revitalise the brands and the main intent is to create brand loyalty.
- ❖ MR helps new establishments and new marketers to test and introduce new products in the existing or in the new market.
- ❖ MR also impacts on the organisation in determining the global market for a good or service. Due diligence in MR may play a vital role in determining and availing a foreign market for the existing products or services.
- ❖ MR has a great impact on the selection of suitable promotional tool to promote goods and services. Due diligence and pilot study in the target market can determine the best promotional tool.
- ❖ MR can impact on controlling the switching practices of loyal customers. The be marketing research can provides thorough information about the changing behaviour of customers and offers suitable suggestions to retain the existing customers.

Findings

- ❖ The study found that market research is an important tool for every marketers to identify the new market place, product or service, new customers and retaining existing customers etc. Almost all the crucial and effective decisions would be taken on the basis of results of market research.
- ❖ It is come to know that market research has a tremendous impact on the decision making process of an organisation. Top level management of any organisation could take prospective decisions on the basis of market research.
- ❖ The study found that various facets, tools and technique have been used in marketing research such as identifying gratification of customers, changes in tastes and preferences, new market place for existing goods, new promotional tools etc.
- ❖ The study found that the market research have been playing an important role in formulating and implementing suitable and remarkable strategies for the betterment of an organisation,
- ❖ The study found that the market research technique have been impacted on the selection of the best distribution channel, and to grab new opportunities in the market for the established marketer.

Suggestions

- ❖ Market research will covers almost all the factors while studying the existing market and identifying new one but some where they may fails to consider the extraneous factors. Hence, it is suggested that extraneous factors such as education qualification, income level, class of customers etc. also be considered because these also impacts on the determining the purchase decision of a particular good or service.
- ❖ Gap is most dangerous and adverse effective factor in taking decisions. Hence, it is suggested that there should not be create any gap between research and implementation of the results (if those are relevant).
- ❖ Change is the rule of the world, so everything will change in this changing environment. Hence, it is suggested that the marketer should conduct research often even though it is high cost activity. There should not be long gap between MR 1 and MR 2.

Conclusion

Marketing research is one of the broader terms in business activities those have tremendous influence on the performance of the organisation and decision making. The decision making is also a crucial part of the administrative of any organisation/marketer/company/business. Decision making process will be completed through selection of an ultimate and best suitable option among several options. From a good marketing research a marketer/organisation can take remarkable decisions for the betterment of future. The term marketing research can be influenced by several factors like customers, demand for and supply of goods, market positions, market strength, market share etc. Market research will be impacting on the decision making of any organisation in terms of formulating strategies, taking developmental and prospective decisions regarding organisation. The effect of MR will be positive because, the selections or determination of a suitable promotional tool can be made through the best practical marketing research. Finally it said that the marketing research has a vital impact on the decision making process of a organisation in every respect.

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